

Enhancing Science Education Using Augmented Reality: Converting 2D Textbook Images into Interactive 3D Models

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Students often face challenges in understanding complex 2D textbook diagrams in subjects such as Physics, Chemistry, and Biology, which can reduce engagement and hinder conceptual learning. Augmented Reality (AR) provides an opportunity to transform static images into interactive 3D models, offering a more immersive and effective learning experience. This study presents the development of a mobile AR application that converts selected 2D images from Grade 11 Science textbooks into 3D models. Built using Unity 3D and Vuforia, the application allows students to scan textbook images and instantly view corresponding 3D objects on their devices. Unlike existing AR educational tools, this application is specifically aligned with the local curriculum and optimized for low-end smartphones, supporting resource-limited classrooms. Preliminary testing with a small group of students demonstrated increased engagement, improved visualization of abstract concepts, and enhanced learning motivation. The findings suggest that AR-based learning tools can bridge gaps in traditional education, making science more accessible and enjoyable. This work highlights the potential of AR as a practical and scalable solution for enhancing classroom learning in developing regions.

Keywords: *Augmented Reality, 3D Models, Science Education, Grade 11, Mobile Learning*